

ANTIANGINAL MEDICINAL PRODUCTS

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Abstract: The article presents data on antianginal drugs, the use of medicinal plants, their pharmacology and pharmacognosy.

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Currently, cardiovascular pathology occupies the first place both in the general structure of diseases and as a cause of mortality. For the treatment of these diseases, medicines are used, which are proposed to be studied. Ischemic heart disease or coronary circulatory insufficiency, episodes of imbalance between the need and the supply of oxygen to the myocardium. As a result, it manifests itself: angina pectoris, stable, unstable, vasospastic (Prinzmetmetal); Acute myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease According to the new International Classification of Diseases published by WHO in 2018, entered into force on January 1, 2022.

A lot of people get sick with coronary heart disease, coronary heart disease includes acute diseases, nonspecific acute coronary heart disease, chronic diseases, old myocardial infarction, ischemic cardiomyopathy, nonspecific chronic coronary heart disease. Many people endure common complications after acute myocardial infarction, such as Dressler syndrome, as well as complications after acute myocardial infarction, for example, pericarditis, rupture of the heart wall, ventricular aneurysm, pulmonary embolism, arrhythmia (cardiogenic shock).

In such heart diseases, antianginal drugs are often used. There are synthetic and natural antianginal agents. As a fast-acting means, synthetic drugs are used more, drugs that provide the myocardium's oxygen demand and its delivery. These are nitrovasodilators (organic nitrates-nitroglicerina (glicerol trinitrat), isosorbid dinitrat, isosorbid mononitrat, pentaeritritil tertranitrat), sydnonymins-molsidomina, nitrate-like- Nitroprusiatul de sodiu; calcium channel blockers (BCC) -Diltiazem, Verapamil, Nifedipina, amlodipina, felodipina, lercanidipina, also inhibitors of If channels, Ivabradina, potassium channel activators, Nicorandil, Pinacidil and many other medicinal products with antianginal action, Amiodarona, beta-blockers: propranolol, metoprolol, atenolol, bisoprolol, carvedilol, coronarodilators, Dipyridamol, Validol,

cardioprotectors-Trimetazidina; antithrombotic drugs-antiplatelet agents-acidul acetilsalicilic, clopidogrel, prasugrel etc.

For a long time, wild medicinal plants have been used by the people for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, such as sweet clover and motherwort. Sweet clover medicinal-Melilotus officinalis.

Melilotus officinalis is a biennial herbaceous plant, a species of the genus Melilotus officinalis of the Legume family of the Moth subfamily. Folk names: burkun, wild buckwheat, yellow clover, female clover, yellow burkun, Italian grass, meadow burkun, burkunets, bottom grass.

Develops an erect branched stem 1-1.5 m high (in culture 1.5—2 m). The taproot penetrates up to 2 m deep. It uses moisture from deep layers, which helps to secrete nectar even in the driest conditions. Leaves with three leaflets. The leaflets are lanceolate, serrated along the edge. At the base of the petiole are stipules (much smaller than the leaflets), whole or toothed. The middle leaflet is on a longer petiole than the lateral ones. Flowers in long and narrow axillary and apical loose racemes, small, drooping, yellow. The calyx is five-toothed. A moth-type corolla.

The extract from the medicinal Melilotus officinalis contains vitamin P, which improves microcirculation and venous blood flow, exhibits anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, analgesic properties, accelerates wound healing and is effective for phlebitis (inflammation of the vein wall). Melilotin, from which coumarin is released during drying by enzymatic cleavage; saponins, tannins, flavonoids, mucus and a little essential oil (primarily in flowers). The effect of the medicinal clover extends mainly to the veins. It can be said that thanks to donnik, capillary resistance (the resistance force of the thinnest blood vessels) increases and the permeability of capillaries decreases.

Leonurus turkestanicus is a traditional medicinal plant. The medicinal properties of motherwort are mentioned in many herbalists of the XV century. The plant was proposed to be used to normalize high blood pressure, calm the rapid heart rate with palpitations occurring against the background of neurosis. The main active ingredients of motherwort grass are flavonoids, iridoids and alkaloids. Motherwort grass has pronounced sedative (soothing) properties. The preparations of the plant have antispasmodic and anticonvulsant effects, slow down the rhythm and increase the strength of heart contractions, have a pronounced hypotensive and cardiogenic effect. Motherwort has a beneficial effect on carbohydrate and fat metabolism, reduces

the level of glucose, lactic and pyruvic acids, cholesterol, total lipids in the blood, normalizes protein metabolism.

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